

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Navigating the shift towards sustainable digital building permits and building logbooks

[version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

Rita Lavikka ⁸, Jeroen Werbrouck⁹

¹Built Environment and Mobility, VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd, Espoo, Uusimaa, 1000, Finland

²University of Cambridge, Cambridge, JJ Thomson Avenue 7, CB3 0RB, UK

³Open Geospatial Consortium EU, Seville, Spain

⁴Human Environment Research (HER), La Salle, Ramon Llull University, Barcelona, Spain

⁵School of Engineering, Cardiff University, Cardiff, UK

⁶CONSTRUCT/Gequaltec, Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

⁷Delft University of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands

⁸Politehnica University of Timisoara, Timișoara, Timiș County, Romania

⁹Ghent University, Ghent, Flanders, Belgium

V1 First published: 31 Mar 2025, 5:90
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18553.1>

Latest published: 04 Aug 2025, 5:90
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18553.2>

Abstract

The architecture, engineering, construction, and operation sectors face significant sustainability challenges. Environmentally, it contributes significantly to greenhouse gas emissions and resource depletion. Socially, it must address issues such as worker safety and community impact. Economically, the sector struggles to balance cost efficiency with sustainable practices. Digital solutions are expected to support sustainable construction. Digital building permits (DBP) and digital building logbooks (DBL) provide examples of digital solutions that support sustainable construction and building management. DBP and DBL are intertwined to enhance the efficiency and transparency of the construction and building management processes. However, research on how DBP and DBL can address sustainability in practice is limited. To address this research gap, this study uses the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as an analytical framework for the sustainability of DBP and DBL. The research consisted of four phases. First, an expert group identified and selected the SDGs related to DBP and DBL. Then, the experts identified the relevant targets of the selected SDGs. Subsequently, the expert group specified the DBP and DBL practices that supported the relevant targets. Finally, the expert group organised a workshop with external experts in the study

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2	3
version 2 (revision) 04 Aug 2025			 view
version 1 31 Mar 2025	 view		

1. **Rupesh Kumar** , Jindal Global University, Sonipet, India
2. **Muhammad Shafique**, Brunel University London, Middlesex, UK
3. **Adrian Wildenauer** ,

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

area to verify the practices supporting the SDGs. The study identified DBP and DBL practices contributing to achieving 10 SDGs: 3, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 16, and 17. The findings suggest that DBL and DBL practices provide opportunities for environmental, social, and economic sustainability; however, further empirical research is needed. The study concluded that DBP and DBL practices can enhance energy management, reduce carbon emissions, improve resource utilisation, and reduce waste. They also support creating a built environment that is user-friendly and remotely accessible, as well as offering financial benefits and improving efficiency and transparency while minimising errors from human interpretation through automation.

Plain language summary

The Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operations sector faces several big challenges when it comes to sustainability. Environmentally, it is a major contributor to greenhouse gas emissions and uses up a lot of natural resources. Socially, it needs to ensure worker safety and consider the impact on local communities. Economically, the sector often struggles to find a balance between keeping costs low and adopting sustainable practices.

Digital solutions are seen as a way to help make construction more sustainable. Two examples of these solutions are digital building permits (DBP) and digital building logbooks (DBL). These tools are designed to make the construction process more efficient and transparent. However, there isn't much research on how well these tools actually promote sustainability.

To fill this gap, a study was conducted using the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as an analysis framework. The research was done in four phases. First, experts identified which SDGs were relevant to DBP and DBL. Then, they pinpointed specific targets within those Goals. After that, the experts specified DBP and DBL practices supporting the relevant targets. Finally, a workshop was held to confirm how DBP and DBL practices support these goals.

The study found that DBP and DBL practices contribute to achieving several SDGs, including good health and well-being, affordable and clean energy, decent work and economic growth, industry innovation and infrastructure, sustainable cities and communities, responsible consumption and production, climate action, peace, justice, and strong institutions, and partnerships for the goals. The study concludes that DBP and DBL practices can enhance energy management, reduce carbon emissions, improve resource utilisation and reduce waste. They also support creating a built environment that is user-friendly and remotely accessible, as well as offering financial benefits and improving efficiency and transparency while minimising errors from human interpretation through automation.

Keywords

Digital building logbook (DBL), digital building permit (DBP), sustainable construction, sustainable building management, sustainable development goals, SDG, data-driven

This article is included in the [Sustainable Places 2024](#) collection.

Corresponding author: Rita Lavikka (rita.lavikka@vtt.fi)

Author roles: **Lavikka R:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Fauth J:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Funding Acquisition, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Toscano M:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Costa G:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Beach T:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Validation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Meda Magalhães P:** Formal Analysis, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Stoter J:** Formal Analysis, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Kaiser SBD:** Formal Analysis, Writing – Review & Editing; **Werbrouck J:** Methodology, Validation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreements No 101056973 (Automated Compliance Checks for Construction, Renovation or Demolition Works – ACCORD), No 101058559 (Change toolkit for digital building permit project - CHEK) and No 101058541 (Digital environment for management of permits and compliance in building and construction - DigiChecks). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101034337 (FUTUREROADS). The UK Participant Cardiff University in Horizon Europe Project ACCORD (grant agreement No 101056973) is supported by UK Research and Innovation grant No 10040207.

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2025 Lavikka R *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Lavikka R, Fauth J, Toscano M *et al.* **Navigating the shift towards sustainable digital building permits and building logbooks [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2025, 5:90 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18553.1>

First published: 31 Mar 2025, 5:90 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18553.1>

Introduction

The architecture, engineering, construction, and operation (AECO) sector faces several sustainability challenges. Environmentally, it contributes significantly to greenhouse gas emissions and the depletion of natural resources (Kanafani *et al.*, 2023). Socially, the AECO sector faces issues such as ensuring worker safety and minimizing negative impacts on local communities (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Economically, the sector often struggles to balance cost efficiency with adopting sustainable practices (Alaloul *et al.*, 2022; Hussain & Hussain, 2023). Therefore, sustainable construction and building management are necessary to address these challenges.

Digital transformation has been shown to support sustainability transformation (Chatzistamoulou, 2023). In the AECO sector, digital building permit (DBP) processes and digital building logbooks (DBL) can contribute to supporting sustainable construction and building management (Crisan *et al.*, 2024). The DBP process involves the use of digital tools and online building permitting and compliance services to streamline and automate the preparation, review, and approval of building permits (Ataide *et al.*, 2023; Fauth *et al.*, 2024; Ullah *et al.*, 2022). The DBP process was found to be more efficient, faster, and transparent (Noardo *et al.*, 2022). On the other hand, DBL encompasses all pertinent building-related data throughout the building's entire lifecycle, offering various stakeholders the specific information they need for different purposes at the appropriate times (Malinovec Puček *et al.*, 2023).

DBP and DBL concepts are intertwined throughout the building lifecycle (Mêda *et al.*, 2024a). For example, when a DBP process begins, DBL data can be used to provide the required datasets. On the other hand, when a DBP is issued, the information can potentially be automatically recorded in the DBL, ensuring that all relevant data about the construction project, including compliance with regulations, are documented from the start. Data-driven is a commonality between the two concepts; the foundational element intersects with several other components, and the relation to BIM is found to be crucial. From an incremental perspective, DBL plays a key role as a Digital Twin enabler at the building scale (Mêda *et al.*, 2021). As the building enters the in-use phase, several services and purposes are expected to be provided by the DBL, whereas real-time data are captured and versioned if required, reflecting any changes or inspections related to the permit (European Commission, 2021; Mêda *et al.*, 2024a; Mêda *et al.*, 2024b; Volt & Toth, 2020).

The availability of consistent and reliable building data can contribute to better design, construction, and management of buildings. Currently, data regarding the physical characteristics of buildings, including information on environmental performance, sustainability, and the data necessary for checking building code compliance, remain unreliable, scarce, and not very accessible. Together, DBP and DBL can establish a common approach that aggregates all related data on a building, such as building materials and energy usage, helping

to identify inefficiencies and to take corrective measures to reduce waste (Mêda *et al.*, 2024a). Building-related data can also help better manage building maintenance by identifying the potential risks related to the lifespan of building systems and materials (European Commission, 2021; Mêda *et al.*, 2024a; Mêda *et al.*, 2024b; Volt & Toth, 2020). In addition, non-digital or paper-based systems require extensive paperwork, multiple physical copies, consumption of other resources for their generation, and numerous in-person visits to various government offices. By contrast, a digital system eliminates the need for physical documents, reduces paper usage, and conserves the trees and water used in paper production. Moreover, by streamlining administrative tasks, digital systems can reduce the energy consumption associated with running a physical office.

Thus, DBP and DBL have the potential to enhance the efficiency, transparency, and sustainability of the construction and building management processes. They promise more precise planning and efficient resource use, reduced waste, and improved building energy management (Crisan *et al.*, 2024; Mêda *et al.*, 2024a; Mêda *et al.*, 2024b; Noardo *et al.*, 2022). However, evidence-based research on the sustainability of DBP and DBL is limited. Several studies have mentioned that DBP processes enhance sustainability (Amor & Dimiyadi, 2021; Malinovec Puček *et al.*, 2023), but they do not explicitly study how and to what extent. Instead, they considered it to be an implicit consequence of the DBP process and DBL implementation. This presents a key research gap in that, thus far, no study has empirically examined the sustainability impacts of DBP and DBL.

To address this research gap, the present study aims to answer the following research question: *What are the sustainability impacts of DBL and DBP and how can those impacts be achieved?* It does this by taking the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations, 2024) as an analytical framework to study the sustainability of DBP and DBL. Therefore, this study contributes to sustainable construction and building management by identifying DBP and DBL practices that contribute to sustainability. This study sets the stage for further research on sustainability in the context of DBP and DBL.

Research process

The research consisted of four phases (Figure 1). In the first phase, the authors, considered as an expert group, searched for literature on the relationship between sustainability and DBP and DBL. The SDGs work as a sustainability analysis framework for structured identification. SDGs consist of 17 goals, each with specific targets to be achieved by 2030. In total, there were 169 targets across all SDGs. During this first phase, the expert group analyzed the relationship between DBP processes and SDGs and between DBL and SDGs. Following an autoethnographic approach (Grosse, 2019), the expert group used their experience and knowledge to identify which SDGs were related to DBP and DBL. The expert group consists of researchers who have studied DBP processes, DBLs, or both

Figure 1. Research process: data collection methods, research phases and outputs.

for at least two years, and most are involved in ongoing projects and collaborations on the topics.

The first round of analysis led to some dissenting opinions among the expert group, but after discussions, ten SDGs were selected to be related to DBP and/or DBL: 3, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 16, and 17.

The second phase focused on identifying relevant targets of the selected SDGs. The selected Goals 3, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 16 and 17 have 95 Targets. The expert group also searched for evidence-based sources – reports, scientific articles, and regulatory documents – to support their claims on the relationships. This phase provides a list of selected targets for the selected SDGs.

In the third phase, the expert group specified DBP and DBL practices to support the relevant targets, underlined with references where possible. The references ranged from scientific literature and project reports to practical and project experience.

In Phase 4, the expert group arranged a workshop to validate the results. The hybrid workshop had 38 participants, approximately half of whom participated onsite and the rest online. The workshop was conducted on September 24, 2024, at the Sustainable Places 2024 conference in Luxembourg. Participants were given a research information sheet explaining the research and their rights. Personal data were not collected, but some background information on the participants was collected anonymously using Slido¹ to ensure that the participants were competent in validating the study results. For example, participants were asked about their country of origin, professional title, and level of knowledge of DBP and DBL. Most of the participants worked in R&D related to the built environment. The professional titles included project managers, research associates, researchers, R&D directors, and a professor. On a scale of 1 (no knowledge), 2 (some knowledge), 3 (lots of knowledge), and 4 (experts in the field), participants' levels of knowledge of DBP and DBL varied. However, most participants had significant knowledge of either DBPs or DBLs. The participants came from the following European countries and regions:

Luxembourg, Portugal, the UK, the Netherlands, Spain (including Catalonia), France, Italy, Poland, Germany, and Belgium.

The workshop consisted of two parts. The first part, 1.5 hours, included an introduction consisting of the research information sheet (10 min), a presentation of SDGs (20 min), and six project presentations on DBP and DBL from ongoing R&D projects (60 min). After the first part, there was a 30-minute coffee break. The second part of the workshop started with collecting the background information on the participants with Slido (20 min) and then continued with group discussions to validate the connection between SDGs and DBP processes and DBLs (70 min). The participants were not shown the analysis that the expert group had done, but they had the opportunity to make their observations, which the expert group then compared with its own findings after the workshop. During the group discussions, the participants could select from three options to indicate how they saw the relationship between each SDG and DBP and each SDG and DBL: 0 (no relationship), 1 (implicitly related), or 2 (explicitly related). The exercise was performed on Miro² which included two tables: one for analyzing the relationship between SDGs and DBP and one table for analyzing the relationship between SDGs and DBL. Both tables' columns included the scale numbers (0, 1, and 2) and rows included the 17 SDGs. Mainly the discussion facilitators made notes to tables based on the group discussions. However, the participants could also access the tables themselves, but only a few added any content there.

Results

This section reports findings regarding the relationship between SDGs and DBP and/or DBL. SDGs 7, 9, 11, and 13 had the most evident relationship to DBP and DBL practices. The results originated from the expert group and workshop discussions. The workshop participants agreed that DBP processes and DBLs can enhance sustainability in the AECO sector. They pointed out how DBP and DBL can improve the traceability of materials, reduce environmental impacts, and promote circularity in construction. The participants strongly emphasized data transparency and interoperability, which could further

¹ <https://www.slido.com/>

² <https://miro.com/app/dashboard/>

streamline sustainable practices. These workshop findings were aligned with those of the expert group.

Supplementary Table 1 lists those SDGs and targets (target descriptions are directly quoted) that were identified as linked to sustainable DBP or DBL practices through evidence-based references (marked after the name of the goal), the expert group and/or workshop discussions. The right column of Table 1 describes the DBP and DBL practices that contribute to achieving ten SDGs: 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), 10 (Reduced Inequalities), 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), 13 (Climate Action), 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions) and 17 (Partnerships for the Goals).

The following paragraphs briefly summarise the findings regarding the relationship between DBP and DBL to the targets of the selected SDGs and sustainable practices.

Regarding SDG 3, “Good Health and Well-Being,” and its chosen targets of 3.4, 3.6, 3.8, and 3.9, it was found that DBP processes can support universal health coverage by ensuring that health facilities are safe and comply with health standards (Soliman-Junior *et al.*, 2020; Soliman-Junior *et al.*, 2021). DBL, a Digital Twin enabler, captures data related to soil properties, toxicity of used materials, and building air quality, thereby supporting users’ health and safety. In general, digital services have ensured access to public services despite physical restrictions during the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting the importance of digital systems in crises.

Regarding SDG 7, “Affordable and Clean Energy,” and its chosen Targets 7.1-7.3, it was found that DBPs, while not directly related to energy services, influence the planning and construction of energy-efficient buildings, and the incorporation of renewable energy sources such as geo-energy (Majuri *et al.*, 2020). Building codes and regulations within the permit process can mandate energy-efficient designs, materials, and technologies, thereby reducing energy consumption. However, research indicates discrepancies between the permitted energy consumption calculations and actual measurements (Ruusala *et al.*, 2018). Permits also facilitate the installation of renewable energy systems, thereby contributing to a sustainable energy mix (Chen *et al.*, 2024; Li & Feng, 2023). Regarding the SDG7 targets, 7.a and 7.b, DBP processes are national mechanisms with some similarities (Bloch & Fauth, 2023; Fauth *et al.*, 2023a; Fauth *et al.*, 2023b; Fauth & Soibelman, 2022; Noardo *et al.*, 2022). They can facilitate knowledge transfer and capacity building, which are essential for deploying energy efficiency and renewable energy technologies. Enforcing regulations for energy-efficient materials and technologies through building permits promotes clean energy adoption and supports investment in energy infrastructure.

Regarding SDG 8, “Decent Work and Economic Growth,” and its chosen Targets 8.1-8.5, it was identified that DBP processes

ensure safety and regulatory compliance while also boosting economic productivity by fostering innovation, efficiency, and the use of sustainable materials (Fauth *et al.*, 2024). Digital technologies can streamline the permitting process, reduce bureaucratic barriers, and facilitate SME growth (Ataide *et al.*, 2023; Beach *et al.*, 2024; Beach *et al.*, 2020). This can boost economic activity and job creation (World Bank Group, 2020; World Bank Group, 2024). Digitalisation enhances transparency and efficiency, making regulatory navigation easier for entrepreneurs and simplifying compliance. Digitalising the building permit process reduces paper usage and streamlines operations, leading to efficient resource use. It enhances data collection and analysis, and informs sustainable urban planning and construction. Digitalisation also improves monitoring and enforcement of environmental regulations, creates tech job opportunities, and improves service access for more people.

Regarding SDG 9, “Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure,” and its chosen targets 9.1-9.5, it was discovered that DBP supports resilient infrastructure by enhancing project efficiency and transparency and reducing delays and costs. This ensures that new constructions meet modern sustainability and resilience standards, foster innovation through smart technologies, and ensure compliance with building codes and safety regulations. Automated code compliance checks verify adherence to seismic and sustainability standards (Amor & Dimiyadi, 2021; Patlakas *et al.*, 2024). DBP processes support digital transformation, improve resource-use efficiency, and encourage clean and environmentally sound technologies and industries (Ataide *et al.*, 2023; Crisan *et al.*, 2024). Innovations such as applied computing for code compliance checking can boost the R&D workforce and increase public and private R&D spending (Amor & Dimiyadi, 2021).

Regarding SDG 10, “Reduced Inequalities,” and its chosen Targets 10.2 and 10.3, it was found that DBP processes and DBL provide insights into built stock, its condition, occupancy, and costs, aiding decision making. Thus, they enhance transparency, reduce discriminatory practices, and ensure equal opportunities.

Regarding SDG 11, “Sustainable Cities and Communities,” and its chosen targets 11.1-11.7, and 11. a, the analysis showed that DBP processes streamlined housing project approvals, facilitating affordable housing development and access to basic services, leading to efficient resource use and faster housing delivery. Digitalising the permit process enhances urban planning efficiency and transparency, facilitates citizen participation and developer compliance (Eirinaki *et al.*, 2018). Digital processes enhance transparency and accountability, ensuring that buildings meet sustainability and resilience standards. Streamlining the permit process reduces time and cost, aiding developers in the least-developed countries. This fosters efficient use of local materials and sustainable building practices (cddb, 2019; Olanrewaju Yusuf *et al.*, 2021).

Regarding SDG 12, “Responsible Consumption and Production”, and its chosen Targets 12.2 and 12.5-12.8, it was discovered

that a digital permit process reduces the environmental impact of construction by minimising waste, optimising material use, and ensuring efficient resource use. It also provides better data for resource management and mandates the reuse of materials. Enhanced accessibility and transparency promote awareness of sustainable practices and regulations (Hradil *et al.*, 2024), aligning with development goals. Selective demolition permits the reuse of recoverable materials based on data availability and DBL.

Regarding SDG 13, “Climate Action,” and its chosen Targets 13.1-13.3, digitalising the permit process can reduce construction’s environmental impact by minimising waste, optimising material use, and ensuring efficient resource use. It also provides improved data and analytics for resource management (Gillingham *et al.*, 2021; Hradil, 2023; Hradil *et al.*, 2024).

Regarding SDG 16, “Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions,” and its chosen targets of 16.6, 16.7, and 16.10, it was identified that digitalising the permit process improves transparency in government spending and budget implementation, ensuring effective use of resources for sustainable development (World Bank Group, 2020; World Bank Group, 2024). It enhances citizen engagement and inclusivity in local governance and promotes transparency and accountability. Digital platforms provide better access to information and facilitate informed public participation in decision-making (Eirinaki *et al.*, 2018).

Regarding SDG 17, “Partnerships for the Goals” and its chosen Targets 17.1 and 17.6, it was concluded that DBPs and DBLs enhance global collaboration in the building sector by offering a unified platform for data sharing throughout the building lifecycle. This standardisation promotes interoperability and cooperation, thereby aligning sustainability and efficiency efforts worldwide. (World Bank Group, 2020; World Bank Group, 2024)

Discussion

In general, digital technologies can support the achievement of the SDGs (Mantovani Ribeiro *et al.*, 2021). They can help identify and agree on the most sustainable ways to work, build appropriate skills across stakeholder groups, attract finance, and ensure practical processes for multi-stakeholder engagement at all stages of building construction. This study supports these findings in the context of DBP and DBL technologies, which provide opportunities for environmental, social, and economic sustainability. Environmentally, they can help enhance energy management, reduce carbon emissions, and improve resource utilisation and waste reduction. Socially, they can promote social inclusion by creating an accessible, user-friendly, and remotely accessible built environment. Economically, they can offer cost savings and long-term financial benefits, streamlining permit application and building management processes, and improving efficiency and transparency while minimising human error or differences due to human interpretation through automated data handling. However, it needs to be noted that digitalisation also has negative environmental impacts.

For example, data storage has environmental impacts due to cooling servers’ high energy and water usage. Although solutions such as using renewable energy to power data centres are being studied to counteract this impact, more research is needed to understand the environmental impact of digitalisation.

Although this paper has envisioned a future in which digital means support the achievement of sustainable construction, challenges exist in the implementation of DBP processes and DBLs. These challenges can be grouped into initial implementation costs, data security, user adoption, and interoperability and provide the corresponding legislative framework for its correct deployment. The initial setup costs, which can be significant, include software development, hardware installation, and staff training. Data security and privacy concerns may arise owing to the storage of sensitive building data in a digital format. The digitalisation of building permits varies across Europe. Some regions adopt Artificial Intelligence (AI), whereas others use PDFs. The need for harmonisation at the European level is crucial for efficiency. Furthermore, ensuring compatibility and seamless data exchange between software platforms and building systems presents interoperability challenges. Therefore, solutions are needed to create strategies that support stakeholders in adopting digital solutions, ensuring the protection of sensitive information, addressing potential user resistance, and enhancing digital literacy. Thus, solutions for seamless data integration across platforms are needed, especially when considering multi-asset DBLs (e.g., for infrastructure), consisting of multiple lower-level DBLs. A lack of familiarity with digital tools among building controls, permit applicants and management staff can also hinder user adoption. The digital divide, which affects people living in poverty (SDG 1), especially in rural areas and developing countries, is also a challenge. Thus, an improved digital infrastructure is crucial to ensure equitable access to DBPs and DBLs.

As data-driven concepts, DBP and DBL can reshape the way production, consumption, and living occur. However, data infrastructure platforms and governance frameworks are required to facilitate data pooling, access, and sharing. In the European Union, data spaces will play this role. Following Europe’s strategy for the digital age, the legal framework is being adjusted, and concerning the built environment, the common European Green Deal Data Space³ is developing a highly accurate digital model of Earth, on top of which all other layers will stand. Currently, there are no common data spaces for construction or built environments. This situation may not be an issue if the required data are captured, stored, and managed in several data spaces. Nevertheless, understanding these boundaries may be challenging and raises several issues. However, if a construction/built environment is set in a similar situation with boundaries, defining the borders of this data space might be extremely difficult. All these ongoing discussions are relevant and constitute challenges for the system architecture

³ European Green Deal Data Space, <https://green-deal-dataspace.eu/>, accessed 23.10.2024.

and data management systems of DBP and DBL. The Rolling Plan for ICT Standardization 2024⁴ considers four key processes for all actions: “Data Governance”, “Data Discovery”, “Data Sharing”, and “Data Usage”. All of these need to be evaluated from the data spaces and DBP/DBL perspectives. This paper focused mainly on the “Data Usage” process, namely, supporting the accomplishment of the UN SDGs’ Targets, but it is paramount to work with the other processes to tackle the challenges.

Conclusions

This study addresses the following research question: “*What are the sustainability impacts of DBL and DBP, and how can those impacts be achieved?*”. To this end, we explored the sustainability of DBP and DBL by applying the UN’s SDGs as an analytical framework.

The findings of this study are that DBP and DBL contribute, both directly and indirectly, to SDGs 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), 13 (Climate Action), 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions), and 17 (Partnerships for the Goals). This study documents how these sustainable impacts of DBP and DBL can be achieved. These findings indicate that digitalising building permits and logbooks provides environmental, social, and economic sustainability. However, the effects of DBP and DBL remain to be determined. The value of digitalisation can only be measured once digital transformation has been completed and digitalisation is in place. During the transformation process, the impacts of DBP and DBL are difficult to measure, even though predictions can be made. Overall, the findings indicated that DBP processes and DBL are part of a broader digital transformation that can support sustainability.

The primary impact of this study is that it provides an outline framework and encouragement for DBP and DBL research communities to begin assessing their work against SDGs. This will enable both the quantitative and qualitative assessment of DBP and DBL research as it enters adoption across

Europe. However, key future work in this area is needed to further develop and validate methods to assess DBL and DBP implementation against the relevant SDGs.

Additionally, the findings provide implicit evidence that DBP and DBL are increasingly aligned with the three current European initiatives and strategies. One of them is Europe’s fit for the digital age. DBP and DBL support the EU’s digital transformation by standardising data collection, management, and sharing across the construction sector. This harmonisation facilitates transparency, trust, and informed decision-making. Another initiative is the European Green Deal and its Renovation Wave, which aims to improve the energy efficiency of buildings. DBP and DBL can support integrating data from energy performance certificates, smart readiness indicators, and building renovation passports, supporting Green Deal’s goals of reducing carbon emissions and promoting sustainable building practices. Finally, DBL can contribute to the New Circular Economy Action Plan initiative by providing a comprehensive repository of building-related data. These data help track materials and resources, promote reuse and recycling, and support the lifecycle management of buildings.

Ethical consideration

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability

Extended data

Repository name: ACCORD project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15078988>

This project contains the following extended data:

Supplementary Table 1 (The selected targets of the selected SDGs and DBP and DBL practices with evidence-based references)

Workshop data (Data collected during a workshop on Digital Building Logbooks and Permit Processes for Sustainability. The workshop was held in Sustainable Places on the 24th of September 2024 in Luxembourg)

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0) (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

⁴ Rolling plan for ICT standardization, <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation>, accessed 23.10.2024.

References

- Alaloul WS, Musarat MA, Rabbani MBA, *et al.*: **Assessment of economic sustainability in the construction sector: evidence from three developed countries (the USA, China, and the UK)**. *Sustainability*. 2022; **14**(10): 6326. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Amor R, Dimiyadi J: **The promise of Automated Compliance Checking**.

Developments in the Built Environment. 2021; **5**: 100039.

[Publisher Full Text](#)

Ataide M, Braholli O, Siegele D: **Digital transformation of building permits: current status, maturity, and future prospects**. *Buildings*. 2023; **13**(10): 2554. [Publisher Full Text](#)

- Beach TH, Hippolyte JL, Rezgui Y: **Towards the adoption of automated regulatory compliance checking in the built environment.** *Automat Constr.* 2020; **118**: 103285.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Beach T, Yeung J, Nisbet N, et al.: **Digital approaches to construction compliance checking: validating the suitability of an ecosystem approach to compliance checking.** *Adv Eng Inform.* 2024; **59**: 102288.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Bloch T, Fauth J: **The unbalanced research on digitalization and automation of the building permitting process.** *Adv Eng Inform.* 2023; **58**: 102188.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- cdbb: **D-COM: digital COMPLIANCE D-COM: digitisation of requirements, regulations and compliance checking processes in the built environment final report.** 2019; **104**.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Chatzistamoulou N: **Is digital transformation the Deus ex machina towards sustainability transition of the European SMEs?** *Ecol Econ.* 2023; **206**: 107739.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Chen L, Hu Y, Wang R, et al.: **Green building practices to integrate renewable energy in the construction sector: a review.** In: *Environmental chemistry letters*. Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH, 2024; **22(2)**: 751–784.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Crisan A, Fauth J, Deac-Kaiser SB: **Sustainability in the context of BIM-Enabled Digital Building Permits.** In: M. di Prisco, S.-H. Chen, I. Vayas, S. K. Shukla, A. Sharma, N. Kumar, C. M. Wang, & Z.-D. Cui (Eds.), *4th International Conference "Coordinating Engineering for Sustainability and Resilience" & Midterm Conference of CircularB "Implementation of Circular Economy in the Built Environment"*. Springer Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering, 2024; 679–689.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Eirinaki M, Dhar S, Mathur S, et al.: **A building permit system for smart cities: a cloud-based framework.** *Comput Environ Urban Syst.* 2018; **70**: 175–188.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- European Commission: **Study on the development of a European Union framework for Digital Building Logbooks - final report.** 2021.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Fauth J, Bloch T, Noardo F, et al.: **Taxonomy for building permit system - organizing knowledge for building permit digitalization.** *Adv Eng Inform.* 2024; **59**: 102312.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Fauth J, Bloch T, Soibelman L: **Process model for international building permit benchmarking and a validation example using the Israeli building permit process.** *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management.* 2023a; **31(13)**: 121–139.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Fauth J, Pasetti Monizza G, Malacarne G: **Understanding processes on Digital Building Permits - a case study in South Tyrol.** *Building Research and Information.* 2023b; **51(5)**: 518–532.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Fauth J, Soibelman L: **Conceptual framework for building permit process modeling: lessons learned from a comparison between Germany and the United States regarding the as-is building permit processes.** *Buildings.* 2022; **12(5)**: 638.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Gillingham KT, Huang P, Buehler C, et al.: **The climate and health benefits from intensive building energy efficiency improvements.** *Sci Adv.* 2021; **7(34)**: eabg0947.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Grosse H: **An insider's point of view: autoethnography in the construction industry.** *Construction Management and Economics.* 2019; **37(9)**: 481–498.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Hradil P: **AC(CO2)RD tool (<https://extgit.vtt.fi/petr.hradil/ac-co2-rd>).** VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, 2023.
[Reference Source](#)
- Hradil P, Lavikka R, Mäkeläinen T: **Towards automated building lifecycle assessment calculation.** In: F. Noardo & J. Fauth (Eds.), *Digital Building Permit Conference 2024*. European Network for Digital Building Permit (EUNet4DBP). 2024; 61–66.
[Reference Source](#)
- Hussain A, Hussain I: **Sustainability assessment for construction projects: a cost-sustainability tradeoff approach.** *J Clean Prod.* 2023; **423**: 138721.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Kanafani K, Magnes J, Lindhard SM, et al.: **Carbon emissions during the building construction phase: a comprehensive case study of construction sites in Denmark.** *Sustainability.* 2023; **15(14)**: 10992.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Li Y, Feng H: **GIS for the potential application of renewable energy in buildings towards net zero: a perspective.** *Buildings.* 2023; **13(5)**: 1205.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Majuri P, Kumpula A, Vuorisalo T: **Geoenergy permit practices in Finnish municipalities – challenges with good governance.** *Energy Strategy Reviews.* 2020; **32**: 100537.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Malinovec Puček M, Khoja A, Bazzan E, et al.: **A data structure for Digital Building Logbooks: achieving energy efficiency, sustainability, and smartness in buildings across the EU.** *Buildings.* 2023; **13(4)**: 1082.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Mantovani Ribeiro DMN, Hourneaux Junior F, Lara Cunha CL, et al.: **Digital sustainability: how Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) support Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) assessment in municipalities.** *Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance.* 2021; **23(3)**: 229–247.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Mêda P, Calvetti D, Hjelseth E, et al.: **Incremental digital twin conceptualisations targeting data-driven circular construction.** *Buildings.* MDPI, 2021; **11(11)**: 554.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Mêda P, Fauth J, Schranz C, et al.: **Digital Building Permits and Digital Building Logbooks – clustering the challenges and requirements for alignment.** *Proceedings of the 2024 European Conference on Computing in Construction.* 2024a.
[Reference Source](#)
- Mêda P, Fauth J, Sousa H, et al.: **When DBP meets DBL conceptual alignment at the process level.** In: F. Noardo & J. Fauth (Eds.), *European Network for Digital Building Permits.* 2024; 29–31.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Noardo F, Guler D, Fauth J, et al.: **Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: getting awareness through a critical state of the art review.** *Building and Environment.* Elsevier Ltd, 2022; **213**: 108854.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Olanrewaju Yusuf S, Adamu Musa M, Chimdi Adindu C, et al.: **A systematic literature review approach on the role of digitalization in construction infrastructure and sustainable city development in developing countries.** *8th Zero Energy Mass Custom Housing (ZEMCH) International Conference*, United Arab Emirates University Ain, UAE, Dubai, UAE. 2021; 1075–1093.
[Reference Source](#)
- Patlakas P, Christovasilis I, Riparbelli L, et al.: **Semantic web-based Automated Compliance Checking with integration of Finite Element Analysis.** *Adv Eng Inform.* 2024; **61**: 102448.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ruusala A, Laukkarinen A, Vinha J: **Energy consumption of Finnish schools and daycare centers and the correlation to regulatory building permit values.** *Energy Policy.* 2018; **119**: 183–195.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Soliman-Junior J, Formoso CT, Tzortzopoulos P: **A semantic-based framework for automated rule checking in healthcare construction projects.** *Canadian Journal of Civil Engineering.* 2020; **47(2)**: 202–214.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Soliman-Junior J, Tzortzopoulos P, Baldauf JP, et al.: **Automated Compliance Checking in healthcare building design.** *Autom Constr.* 2021; **129**: 103822.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ullah K, Witt E, Lill I: **The BIM-based building permit process: factors affecting adoption.** *Buildings.* 2022; **12(1)**: 45.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
- United Nations: **The 17 Goals.** 2024.
[Reference Source](#)
- Volt J, Toth Z: **Definition of the digital building logbook: report 1 of the study on the development of a European Union framework for buildings' digital logbook.** 2020.
[Reference Source](#)
- World Bank Group: **Doing business 2020 - comparing business regulation in 190 economies.** 2020.
[Reference Source](#)
- World Bank Group: **Dealing with construction permits.** Subnational studies - measuring business regulations. 2024.
[Reference Source](#)
- Zhang M, Shi R, Yang Z: **A critical review of vision-based Occupational Health and Safety monitoring of construction site workers.** In: *Safety Science.* Elsevier B.V, 2020; **126**: 104658.
[Publisher Full Text](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 25 June 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.20061.r55473>

© 2025 Shafique M. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Muhammad Shafique

Brunel University London, Middlesex, UK

OVERALL REVIEW RESULT

This is a well-structured and written article. However, as the main drawback, it isn't easy to recognise the importance of the research results. Reading the conclusions, the study has not contributed significantly to new findings that are not already available in the existing literature, and the overall outcome sounds trivial. For example, the authors have ended up stating: "The study documents how these sustainable impacts of DBP and DBL can be achieved"; but how these will be achieved are not explained in details. Also, I believe it is very important to highlight content on the importance of incorporating methods.

I hope that this feedback will be helpful as you look to strengthen your research efforts.

MORE SPECIFIC COMMENTARY

The paper aims to answer the following research question: *What are the sustainability impacts of DBL and DBP and how can those impacts be achieved?*

The aim is to explore sustainable construction and building management by identifying DBP and DBL practices that contribute to sustainability.

The structure of this paper is suitable.

The English language used in the manuscript is good enough to convey the idea of the paper without critical mistakes in grammar, word selection, and typing. Still, a second English proofread is suggested.

Title - It is reasonable.

Keywords - They are reasonable.

It is still unclear how the research questions relate to the statements in introduction section and how the current article goes beyond other existing literature in this area. To address this issue, please try to embed the questions into the body of the text presented in introduction section.

Research Process;

It is essential to elaborate on how the experts were selected and which sampling method was used to select experts?

It is important to clearly give detail information on methods selection for methodology section.

While the work appears technically solid and well-organized, with relevant features and structured categories, the data collection and processing protocols are not described in sufficient technical detail. The article lacks the following:

- Clarification on whether data were normalized or standardized.
- No mention of data cleaning, anonymization, or aggregation methods.
- Uncertainty regarding the temporal resolution of data.
- The tool or platform used for data processing and visual analytics is mentioned vaguely but not named or described.

Conclusion

Were there any limitations in your research work?

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Partly

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

No source data required

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Sustainability, Life-cycle Energy and Environmental Assessment (LCA), Circular Economy, Sustainable Construction

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 08 Jul 2025

Rita Lavikka

We thank the reviewer for the constructive comments, which helped us improve our article. Below, we provide our more detailed responses to each review comment. Review comment: "This is a well-structured and written article. However, as the main drawback, it isn't easy to recognise the importance of the research results. Reading the conclusions, the study has not contributed significantly to new findings that are not already available in the existing literature, and the overall outcome sounds trivial. For example, the authors have ended up stating: "The study documents how these sustainable impacts of DBP and DBL can be achieved"; but how these will be achieved are not explained in details. Also, I believe it is very important to highlight content on the importance of incorporating methods. I hope that this feedback will be helpful as you look to strengthen your research efforts." Our response: We thank the reviewer for this thoughtful feedback. In response, we have revised the Discussion and Conclusions sections to more clearly articulate the novelty and significance of our findings. We now emphasise that our study is the first to systematically map Digital Building Permit (DBP) and Digital Building Logbook (DBL) practices to specific UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), providing a structured and replicable framework for sustainability assessment. Please see also Supplementary Table 1. We refined the Conclusions section to answer both research questions explicitly and added a new paragraph on the study's impact: The impact of this study is twofold. First, it introduces a structured and replicable framework for assessing the sustainability of DBP and DBL practices by explicitly mapping them to specific SDG targets. This goes beyond prior literature, which often treats sustainability as an implicit benefit rather than a measurable outcome. Second, the study demonstrates how expert-driven analysis and stakeholder validation can be used to identify actionable DBP and DBL practices that support environmental, social, and economic sustainability. By doing so, the paper lays a foundation for future empirical research and policy development, supporting the alignment of digital construction tools with global sustainability objectives. This will enable both the quantitative and qualitative assessment of DBP and DBL research as it enters adoption across Europe. However, key future work is needed in this area to develop further and validate methods for assessing DBL and DBP implementation against the relevant SDGs. We also added more explanation about the uniqueness of our method to the Research process section. Review comment: "The paper aims to answer the following research question: What are the sustainability impacts of DBL and DBP and how can those impacts be achieved? The aim is to explore sustainable construction and building management by identifying DBP and DBL practices that contribute to sustainability. The structure of this paper is suitable. The English language used in the manuscript is good enough to convey the idea of the paper without critical mistakes in grammar, word selection, and typing. Still, a second English proofread is suggested." Our response: We corrected grammatical mistakes, shortened long sentences and made a second English proofread. Review comment: "Title - It is reasonable. Keywords - They are reasonable. It is still unclear how the research questions relate to the statements in introduction section and how the current article goes beyond other existing literature in this area. To address this issue, please try to embed the questions into the body of the text presented in introduction section." Our response: We thank the reviewer for this insightful comment. In response, we have revised the final paragraph of the Introduction to explicitly embed the research question and clarify how it emerges from the identified research gap.

We also added a sentence earlier in the Introduction to highlight the novelty of our approach compared to existing literature. These changes aim to improve the logical flow from problem identification to research objective and to better position our contribution within the broader academic discourse. Review comment: "Research Process; It is essential to elaborate on how the experts were selected and which sampling method was used to select experts? It is important to clearly give detail information on methods selection for methodology section." Our response: We appreciate the reviewer's request for clarification. In response, we have revised the Methodology section to provide more detail on both the expert selection process and the rationale for our methodological choices. We now clarify that the expert group was selected using purposive sampling, targeting individuals with at least two years of experience in research or implementation of digital building permits (DBP) and/or digital building logbooks (DBL). Most experts were actively involved in ongoing European R&D projects related to these topics. We have added a justification for using a four-phase mixed-method approach combining literature review, expert elicitation, SDG mapping, and stakeholder validation. This approach was chosen to ensure both theoretical grounding and practical relevance. The methodological approach was designed to bridge the gap between theory and practice. It began with a structured literature review and SDG mapping, followed by expert-driven identification of relevant targets and practices. The final phase involved a hybrid workshop with 38 participants from across Europe to validate the findings. This multi-phase design ensured that the results were both evidence-based and grounded in stakeholder perspectives. Review comment: "While the work appears technically solid and well-organized, with relevant features and structured categories, the data collection and processing protocols are not described in sufficient technical detail. The article lacks the following: ○ Clarification on whether data were normalized or standardized. ○ No mention of data cleaning, anonymization, or aggregation methods. ○ Uncertainty regarding the temporal resolution of data. ○ The tool or platform used for data processing and visual analytics is mentioned vaguely but not named or described." Our response: We thank the reviewer for highlighting the need for greater transparency in our data handling and processing protocols. In response, we have revised the Research process section to include the following clarifications: As the study was qualitative in nature and based on expert elicitation and workshop validation, numerical data normalisation or standardisation was not applicable. However, we have clarified this explicitly in the revised text. We now specify that no personal data was collected during the workshop. Background information was gathered anonymously using Slido, and all responses were aggregated at the group level to ensure privacy. We have clarified that the data collected reflects a single-point-in-time assessment conducted during the Sustainable Places 2024 conference on September 24, 2024. We now explicitly state that Slido was used for collecting participant background data, and Miro was used for collaborative SDG mapping during the workshop. These tools were chosen for their accessibility and ability to support hybrid participation. Review comment: "Conclusion - Were there any limitations in your research work?" Our response: Yes, we acknowledge several limitations in our research, which we have now explicitly stated in the revised Conclusions section. The study is based on expert elicitation and workshop validation, which, while rich in insight, may introduce subjectivity and limit generalisability. The workshop participants were primarily from European countries, which may limit the applicability of findings to other regions with different regulatory or technological contexts. The data reflect a single-point-in-time assessment conducted during the Sustainable Places 2024 conference. As such, the findings may not capture evolving

practices or future developments in DBP and DBL. The study does not include longitudinal tracking of DBP/DBL implementation impacts, which would be valuable for assessing sustainability outcomes over time. While tools like Slido and Miro facilitated data collection and collaboration, they also constrained the depth of interaction and granularity of data that could be captured.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 02 April 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.20061.r52624>

© 2025 Kumar R. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Rupesh Kumar

Jindal Global University, Sonipet, Haryana, India

Author needs to cite few important latest papers.

Author needs to support the theory with more explanation.

Author needs to compare the other studies to support its study with latest references.

Author needs to check for grammatical mistakes and avoid using long sentences.

Author needs to see their figures and tables are properly cited.

The method used by author should be unique and give explanation as compared to other work.

Author should check the format of using citations and references as per journal guidelines.

Author should address all the comments given earlier and should provide organized structure of their manuscript.

References

1. Kumar R, Kansara S: Supply chain process of olive oil industry. *International Journal of Management Practice*. 2018; **11** (2). [Publisher Full Text](#)
2. Rajani R, Heggde G, Kumar R: Services Redesign Strategies for Demand and Capacity Management and Impact on Company Performance. *Vision: The Journal of Business Perspective*. 2022. [Publisher Full Text](#)
3. Sharma K, Kumar R, Kumar A, Balabantaray S, et al.: A digital ecosystem for sustainable fruit supply chain in Uttarakhand: a comprehensive review. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*. 2023; **26** (5): 13217-13252 [Publisher Full Text](#)
4. Arora M, Kumar R, Raju T: Identification of issues in the cold chain of Indian frozen food. *International Journal of Logistics Economics and Globalisation*. 2023; **10** (1). [Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Sustainable, Analytics

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 08 Jul 2025

Rita Lavikka

We thank the reviewer for the constructive comments, which helped us improve our article. Below, we provide our more detailed responses to each review comment. Review comment: "Author needs to cite few important latest papers." Our response: Thank you for suggesting that we add a few important, latest papers. We checked Scopus and Google Scholar and identified one new paper addressing the sustainability of digital building permits and logbooks, and added it to the paper: Mêda P, Fauth J, Schranz, et al.: Twinning the path of digital building permits and digital building logbooks – Diagnosis and challenges. *Developments in the Built Environment*. 2024. 10.1016/j.dibe.2024.100573. We also reviewed the ones suggested by the reviewer. The paper by Sharma et al. (2023) is relevant to our study, and we have added it to our paper since it examines digitalisation as an enabler of sustainability in fruit supply chains and proposes technological solutions that can contribute to sustainable horticulture practices. Please see the section Discussion. Three other papers appear to address different types of issues, not our topic: the sustainability impacts of digital building permit (DBP) processes or digital building logbooks (DBL), and strategies for achieving them. We will address each paper in more detail: The paper by Kumar & Kansara (2018) focuses on the optimisation and analysis of supply chain processes in the olive oil industry. This paper is not directly related to our paper in terms of subject matter or methodology, but they are complementary examples of how digitalisation can support sustainability in different sectors. However, as we are not exploring cross-sectoral insights on digital tools for sustainability, we will not use it as a reference, even though Kumar & Kansara's paper is an interesting piece of research. The paper by Rajani et al. (2022) examines the relationship between selected supply chain risks, the utilisation of

service redesign strategies, and their impact on companies. We couldn't find the connection to our paper's topic. The paper by Arora et al. (2023) examines the issues affecting the frozen food cold chain in India and proposes strategies to address these issues, without a primary focus on sustainability. Review comment: "Author needs to support the theory with more explanation." Our response: We appreciate the reviewer's insightful comment. We elaborated on the theoretical underpinnings of how digital transformation supports sustainability in the AECO sector. Please see the Introduction section. Review comment: "Author needs to compare the other studies to support its study with latest references." Our response: We added the reference to Sharma et al. (2023). This is the only comparable study that could be found despite conducting an extensive literature review. Otherwise, we couldn't identify new papers. Review comment: "Author needs to check for grammatical mistakes and avoid using long sentences." Our response: We corrected grammatical errors and condensed lengthy sentences. Review comment: "Author needs to see their figures and tables are properly cited." Our response: We have verified that Figure 1 and Supplementary Table 1 are properly cited, and the technical editors of Open Research Europe have also confirmed this prior to the first publication. Review comment: "The method used by author should be unique and give explanation as compared to other work." Our response: We added more explanation about the uniqueness of our method to the section Research process. Review comment: "Author should check the format of using citations and references as per journal guidelines." Our response: Citations and references have been checked. Also, the technical editors of Open Research Europe check this before publication. Review comment: "Author should address all the comments given earlier and should provide organized structure of their manuscript." Our response: All comments are addressed, and an organised structure of the manuscript is followed. Thank you once again for your review comments that helped us improve our paper.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.